

An Academic Review of Strategic Balances and Power Struggles in the Middle East

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Abstract

The Middle East has long been recognized as a strategically significant area and has become a crucial region that influences global geopolitical and economic dynamics. This area is of great significance in global politics because of its abundant energy resources, strategic positioning, and its involvement in intricate historical battles. The oil and natural gas reserves in the area are crucial for global energy markets, and they have a direct impact on both the economic strength of the nations in the region and global energy security. Hence, political instability or wars in the Middle East may result in volatility in energy prices, vulnerability of the global economy, and restructuring of global power dynamics. The geopolitical significance of the Middle East extends beyond its petroleum resources. The region's geopolitical position has rendered it a highly contested territory for global powers. The Middle East is situated at the crossroads of Asia, Europe, and Africa, making it a crucial hub for global trade routes. The Strait of Hormuz, the Bab-el-Mandeb Strait, and the Suez Canal are crucial waterways for international oil transport. Ensuring the security of these transit areas is essential for global commerce. The security of these areas is crucial for maintaining global economic stability, but it is also a focal point for power conflicts in the area.

Keywords : Middle East, Political Instability, Strategic Importance, Competition Area of Powers, Geopolitical Position

Introduction

Recognizing the strategic significance of the region, local stakeholders have implemented many strategies to safeguard their national interests and enhance their sway in the area. Turkey, driven by the historical impact of the Ottoman Empire and its current geopolitical objectives, persistently asserts its status as a regional power and endeavors to extend its influence in the area via the establishment of energy transmission lines and the deployment of military resources. Within this particular framework, Turkey's significance in the Middle East is crucial

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in relation to regional security, political equilibriums, and energy security. Israel has implemented a plan to address dangers in its vicinity by creating advanced defensive systems and forming diplomatic partnerships that align with its security interests. Israel's security policies have a significant impact not just on the regional level but also on its interactions with global players. Iran is strategically expanding its Shiite influence in the area by extending its presence in countries like Syria, Lebanon, and Yemen. This often leads to confrontations, both direct and indirect, with regional and global powers. The strategic maneuvers undertaken by Iran have a substantial impact on the distribution of power in the Middle East and provide an ongoing risk to the security of the area.

Aim

The strategic objectives of these regional entities also capture the interest of global powers and influence their actions towards the Middle East. The United States maintains a significant military and diplomatic presence in the area to safeguard the security of oil resources and trade routes in the Middle East, as well as to secure the protection of Israel. The US influence in this area extends beyond energy security and is also seen as a component of the pursuit for global dominance. In contrast, Russia has bolstered its influence in the area by its engagement in the Syrian civil war, successfully establishing a lasting presence in the Middle East. This scenario amplifies Russia's sway over the global distribution of power, while also intensifying the ongoing power rivalry in the Middle East. China employs a discreet but efficient approach in the region, primarily relying on economic investments and energy cooperation. This allows China to ensure its energy supply while simultaneously enhancing its influence in the area. China's involvement in the Middle East is seen as a manifestation of its growing influence and economic might in worldwide energy markets.

Methodology

Each advancement in the area has a direct impact on the interests of these influential nations and alters the worldwide distribution of power. Any altercation in the Middle East jeopardizes not just the local area but also worldwide security and economic stability. Hence, it is crucial to constantly monitor and analyze the strategic balances in the Middle East in order to shape regional and global policy. The objective of this research is to get a deeper understanding of how the area influences world politics by examining strategic equilibriums and power conflicts in the Middle East.

Literature Review

This in-depth research serves as a strategic roadmap for comprehending the existing power dynamics in the Middle East and anticipating potential future situations. This analysis examines the strategic objectives of each participant in the area to demonstrate their potential regional and global influence. Additionally, it evaluates the potential consequences of these objectives on regional peace and stability. The analysis also highlights the hazards presented by the continuing wars in the Middle East to worldwide security and economic stability. This study serves as a valuable tool for decision-makers, policy-makers, academics, and researchers. Its purpose is to enhance their comprehension of the intricate power dynamics in the Middle East and enable them to formulate policies informed by these dynamics.

Turkey's Strategic Approach

Turkey's energy policy in the Eastern Mediterranean demonstrate a deliberate and calculated strategy that yields significant outcomes at both the regional and international levels. The substantial natural gas deposits found in the Eastern Mediterranean have significant

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significance for the energy security and economic advancement objectives of the nations in the area. Turkey's active participation in the area becomes more crucial (Doğan, 2020).

Importance of Energy Resources

Turkey meets a large portion of its energy needs through imports, and this situation stands out as an important reason for the country's foreign trade deficit. Natural gas reserves in the Eastern Mediterranean are considered a great opportunity in line with Turkey's goal of increasing energy supply security and reducing energy dependency. Turkey has accelerated its exploration and drilling activities in the areas it claims to be included in its continental shelf and exclusive economic zone (EEZ) in this region (Öztürk, 2019).

Exploration and Drilling Activities

Starting in 2018, Turkey has been actively engaged in extensive exploration and drilling operations with the aim of accessing energy reserves in the Eastern Mediterranean. The aforementioned operations are conducted by drilling vessels known as Fatih, Yavuz, and Kanuni. Turkey has effectively created a significant naval force in the area, therefore enhancing its influence in the Eastern Mediterranean. Turkey's actions have caused tensions, particularly with Greece and the Greek Cypriot Administration of Southern Cyprus (GCASC), and have intensified the struggle over energy resources in the area (Balçı, 2021).

Continental Shelf and Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) Disputes

Turkey and Greece, together with the Greek Cypriot Administration, have significant disputes about the boundaries of the continental shelf and exclusive economic zones (EEZ) in the Eastern

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Mediterranean. Greece and the Greek Cypriot Administration consider Turkey's drilling efforts to be unlawful, while Turkey asserts that these actions are conducted in accordance with its own sovereign rights. The tensions have been further exacerbated by the agreement of understanding that Turkey and Libya signed, which delineates maritime jurisdiction zones. The objective of this agreement is to expand Turkey's maritime jurisdiction in the Eastern Mediterranean and ensure its access to energy resources (Uslu, 2020).

Regional and International Reactions

The energy policies of Turkey in the Eastern Mediterranean are under careful scrutiny not just by Greece and the Greek Cypriot Administration, but also by international entities such as the European Union (EU) and the United States (US). The European Union has issued condemnations against Turkey's drilling operations and demanded an immediate cessation of these activities. The European Union has included economic measures on Turkey as part of its agenda. The United States has issued a cautionary statement, advising Turkey against engaging in actions that may exacerbate tensions in the area (Yılmaz, 2021).

Turkey's Strategic Goals

Turkey's strategic maneuvers in the Eastern Mediterranean are a deliberate attempt to alter the distribution of power in the area, while also aiming to secure access to energy resources and enhance energy self-sufficiency. Turkey has strategically positioned itself as a significant player in the energy rivalry in the area. It is actively working to safeguard its own energy security and maintain its strategic interests in the Eastern Mediterranean (Koru, 2022).

Turkey's strategic approach has a significant impact on the existing dynamics in the Eastern Mediterranean and adds more complexity to the fight for energy resources in the area. Turkey's strategic objectives in this area revolve on achieving energy self-sufficiency, bolstering its

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political and military influence, and safeguarding its interests in the Eastern Mediterranean. Hence, Turkey's activities in the Eastern Mediterranean remain a significant subject of debate in the field of international relations, resonating not just at a regional level but also on a worldwide one (Doğan, 2020).

Turkey's Syria Policy: Strategic Objectives and Applications

Since the beginning of the Syrian civil conflict in 2011, Turkey has formulated its Syria policy with the objective of safeguarding both its regional and national security interests. Turkey, a significant regional player, is actively engaged in the civil conflict in Syria and implements a comprehensive strategy that encompasses military, political, and humanitarian assistance. This strategy is formulated based on Turkey's objectives of safeguarding border security, eradicating terrorist risks, addressing the refugee crisis, and establishing a lasting political resolution in Syria (Erşen, 2020).

Turkey's Strategic Goals

The objective of Turkey's Syria policy is to safeguard its national security interests while also promoting regional stability. Turkey is now using its military operations in Syria to safeguard its borders from terrorist threats. Simultaneously, Turkey is persistently working towards managing the refugee issue and facilitating a political resolution in Syria. These strategic objectives enhance Turkey's regional influence and guarantee its involvement in shaping the future of Syria (Erşen, 2020).

The implementation of this diverse strategy in Turkey's Syria policy strengthens its status as a dominant force in the region and empowers it to actively contribute to the pursuit of a global resolution to the Syrian issue. Nevertheless, the intricate power dynamics in Syria and the involvement of foreign stakeholders persist as obstacles that impede Turkey's ability to

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accomplish these objectives. Turkey's adaptability and diplomatic prowess in its Syria strategy will play a crucial role in shaping future events (Altunışık, 2021).

Türkiye-Azerbaijan Strategic Alliance: Historical, Military and Economic Dimensions

The strategic alliance between Turkey and Azerbaijan is founded upon profound historical and cultural connections, and is exemplified as a robust cooperation encapsulated by the term "two states, one nation". This alliance is founded not only on the principles of brotherhood and shared history, but has also evolved into a comprehensive collaboration including military, diplomatic, and economic domains. Turkey firmly supports the territorial integrity and sovereignty of Azerbaijan, and has further enhanced its strategic interests in the Caucasus area via this partnership (Kösebalaban, 2011).

Diplomatic Support and Balance in the Caucasus

Turkey's assistance to Azerbaijan extended beyond military and economic domains, manifesting prominently in diplomatic spheres as well. Turkey has supported Azerbaijan's legitimate cause in international forums and consistently affirmed that Karabakh rightfully belongs to Azerbaijan. The diplomatic assistance bolstered Azerbaijan's standing on the global stage (Jabali, 2014).

The strategic partnership between Turkey and Azerbaijan has had a substantial impact on the geopolitical equilibrium in the Caucasus region. Although this partnership has bolstered Turkey's power in the area, it has simultaneously exerted pressure on Armenia and those factions that support it. Turkey's proactive involvement in the area is also seen as a strategic maneuver to counterbalance Russia's influence in the Caucasus. Furthermore, Iran's impact in the area has been restricted within the parameters of this alliance (Balcer, 2011).

Israel and Palestine: At the Center of Regional Conflict

The Israel-Palestine conflict is a very intricate matter in the Middle East, including historical, religious, political, and international aspects. This war has not only persisted as a fight between two groups, but has also been influenced by the geopolitical calculations and interventions of regional and global powers, and has become a significant issue for world security and peace (Khalidi, 2006).

Historical Background and Origins of the Conflict

The Israel-Palestine conflict originated from the endeavors of the Zionist movement to create a Jewish nation in Palestine during the late 1800s. The process gained momentum with the dissolution of the Ottoman Empire during World War I. The United Nations' resolution in 1947 to partition Palestine into separate Arab and Jewish states, and the subsequent foundation of the State of Israel in 1948, sparked significant opposition throughout the Arab world. The conflicts that arose after the founding of Israel and the displacement of Palestinians elevated the problem to an international level (Shlaim, 2001).

Israel's Security Strategies

Israel has implemented a comprehensive and multi-faceted security policy since its establishment in 1948, with the aim of ensuring its survival and safety. Israel's security measures amid the volatile geopolitical landscape of the Middle East are focused on addressing regional threats and ensuring the country's military capabilities remains at its peak. The fundamental components of these tactics include the use of military might, deterrence, intelligence gathering, diplomatic engagements, and advanced defensive systems.

The Palestinian Question: A Multidimensional Conflict Area

The Palestinian question should not be just seen as a bilateral dispute between two nations; it is a multifaceted matter that has religious, regional, and global elements. This matter has been influenced by a blend of historical, theological, and political elements and is continuously being modified to align with the diverse objectives of many participants. Hence, it is imperative to analyze the Palestinian question from several viewpoints:

A Problem Between Two Peoples

The Palestinian problem essentially entails a struggle between the Israeli and Palestinian populations about land, identity, and self-determination. Following the formation of Israel in 1948, a significant number of Palestinians were forcibly displaced from their territories and subsequently became refugees. While the Palestinians see this circumstance as a tragic event for their people, Israel characterizes it as their struggle for independence (Khalidi, 1997). Since this point in time, the Palestinians have faced challenges in their efforts to build a sovereign nation and achieve self-determination.

Israel's settlement policies, particularly the establishment of more Jewish communities in the West Bank and the incorporation of East Jerusalem, hinder Palestinian aspirations for self-governance and impede progress towards a two-state resolution. While Palestinians see these settlements as an act of occupation, Israel, driven by historical and theological factors, considers these territories to be its own (Pappe, 2006). Hence, the Palestinian predicament persists as an intensified conflict zone centered on issues of identity and land, representing a battle between two distinct populations.

Iran and Syria: The Axis of Resistance

Iran and Syria are significant nations in the Middle East that constitute a coalition known as the "Axis of Resistance," which opposes the West and Israel. Since the 1979 Iranian Islamic Revolution, these two nations have forged a strengthening strategic partnership. This alliance has a crucial impact on determining the equilibrium and geopolitical dynamics in the area. The phrase "Axis of Resistance" denotes Iran's objective to limit the sway of the Western powers and Israel, in conjunction with its regional allies. The axis in question is founded upon an extensive network that encompasses several factions, including Hezbollah and Hamas. Syria, in particular, has a crucial position in Iran's geopolitical objectives.

Iran's Regional Goals and Strategies

- Iran has used many measures to enhance its influence as a regional hegemon in the Middle East and to accomplish its ideological and political objectives. Iran considers Syria to be a crucial partner and has positioned its connection with Syria as a major component of its "Axis of Resistance."
- The Shia Crescent Strategy is a geopolitical plan by Iran to establish a continuous area of Shia influence extending from Lebanon to Yemen. This policy has become more apparent as Iran consolidates its foothold in Syria. Syria plays a crucial role in this plan as it serves as a strategic conduit for Iran to connect with Hezbollah in Lebanon and get access to the Mediterranean (Gause, 2019).
- Iran perceives Israel as the primary menace in the area and has implemented a range of measures with the objective of curbing Israel's impact. Iran provides assistance and weaponry to anti-Israeli resistance organizations like Hezbollah and Hamas. Syria provides Iran with a crucial location for supplying logistical assistance and conducting training for these organizations (Wehrey, 2018).

The Syrian Civil War and Iran's Role

- The Syrian civil conflict has emerged as a crucial battleground for Iran to expand its influence in the Middle East. The Syrian civil war, which started in 2011, has transformed into a geopolitical contest between regional and global powers. Iran has played a significant role in bolstering the Assad government by providing substantial military and financial assistance to Syria.
- Iran has had a substantial impact on the civil conflict by offering direct military assistance to the Syrian regime. Iran maintains a robust military presence in Syria by deploying the Quds Force of the Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps and Shiite militia factions. These forces have significantly bolstered the endurance of the Assad administration and its resistance against opposition troops (Kamrava, 2020).
- Hezbollah, Iran's partner in Lebanon, has significantly contributed to the Syrian civil war by supporting the Assad government. Hezbollah, with the backing of Iran, has played a significant role in the Syrian conflict by actively engaging in combat and assisting President Assad in achieving success over the opposition forces. Hezbollah's influence in Syria and Lebanon has been strengthened, thus solidifying Iran's dominance in the area (Guzansky, 2020).

The Iran-Syria alliance has significant strategic importance. The partnership between Iran and Syria is seen as a collaboration that has a substantial impact on regional power dynamics. This alliance encompasses not only military, but also political, economic, and ideological aspects. Iran and Syria have a shared political and ideological bond centered on their battle against the West and Israel. This philosophy allows both nations to collaborate as part of the "Axis of Resistance". Iran views Syria as a stronghold of opposition against the Western world and Israel, and consistently offers unwavering assistance to the Assad administration in this respect (Gause, 2019).

Iran and Syria demonstrate cooperation in the economic domain via their economic and energy collaboration. Iran sent substantial financial aid to the nation throughout the Syrian conflict and actively participated in many rehabilitation initiatives in Syria.

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Furthermore, Iran's strategic objective of establishing a route to Lebanon and the Mediterranean via Syria has significant importance in relation to energy corridors (Kamrava, 2020).

Regional and Global Responses

The careful monitoring of the partnership between Iran and Syria is of great interest to other nations in the region as well as global powers. This alliance has had a significant impact on the distribution of power in the Middle East and has elicited responses from other regional entities. Israel see Iran's presence in Syria and the increasing influence of Hezbollah as a clear and immediate danger. Israel periodically carries out aerial attacks against Iranian targets in Syria and endeavors to curtail Iran's influence in the area (Wehrey, 2018).

- **Saudi Arabia and the Gulf States:** Saudi Arabia and the Gulf States strongly oppose Iran's attempts to increase its influence in the area. These nations see the Iran-Syria alliance as a threat to their own security and are establishing regional alliances to counteract this alliance (Guzansky, 2020).
- **The US and Western Response:** The US and Western nations have implemented economic measures against the Assad government and provided assistance to rebel factions with the aim of restricting Iran's involvement in Syria and its impact on the surrounding area. Nevertheless, Iran's impact in Syria persists despite the implementation of these sanctions (Kamrava, 2020).

The concept of the Axis of Resistance refers to a coalition of countries that oppose Western influence in the Middle East and want to maintain a balance of power in the region. The alliance between Iran and Syria, known as the "Resistance Axis," remains intact and significantly influences the geopolitical dynamics in the Middle East. Iran has bolstered its regional influence by providing assistance to the Assad administration throughout the Syrian civil war, so strengthening the "Resistance Axis". This alliance has a vital role in promoting policies that are against Israel and the Western countries. It is a significant factor in defining

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the balance of power in the Middle East area. Nevertheless, this alliance is under vigilant scrutiny by other stakeholders and global forces in the area, leading to a rise in regional tensions.

The strategy of Iran's expansion in the region

Iran is now executing a strategy plan known as the "Shia Crescent" with the aim of extending its influence throughout the Middle East and consolidating its status as a dominant force in the area. The objective of this strategy is to enhance Iran's sway in the Middle East and accomplish its geopolitical objectives by bolstering its influence in areas having a substantial Shia populace. In order to achieve this objective, Iran is executing a range of tactics, such as providing assistance to indigenous Shia factions in the area, forging political and military partnerships, and engaging in regional wars either directly or indirectly.

The Shia Crescent Strategy encompasses the range and goals of its activities. The phrase "Shia Crescent" denotes Iran's strategic objective of extending its Shia influence throughout a geographical region spanning from Lebanon to Yemen. This policy exemplifies Iran's efforts to expand its sphere of influence by leveraging Shia populations across the region and augmenting its political, military, and religious sway in these areas.

- Hezbollah in Lebanon: Hezbollah in Lebanon is a crucial ally for Iran in the area. Hezbollah is a Shiite paramilitary organization that was established and bolstered via the financial, military, and ideological backing provided by Iran. Hezbollah not only has significant political influence in Lebanon, but also serves as a prominent symbol of resistance against Israel. Hezbollah has played a significant role on behalf of Iran in the Syrian civil war, aggressively supporting the Assad government (Wehrey, 2018).

Iran's political influence on Shia militias in Iraq has grown significantly since the US invasion of Iraq in 2003. Shiite militia organizations, including Shaabi (Popular Mobilization Forces), were formed and reinforced in Iraq via the backing of Iran. These militias have emerged as a significant participant in Iraq's internal politics and security framework. Iran seeks to exert

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influence on Iraq's political system by using these militias and guiding Iraq in line with its own geopolitical objectives (Kamrava, 2020).

Iran seeks to solidify its strategic position in the region by providing assistance to the Assad administration in Syria, with the intention of establishing a lasting presence in the nation. Iran, a prominent backer of the Assad administration in the Syrian civil war, has sent both military and financial aid to Assad in order to secure his continued existence. Throughout this process, Iran has systematically coordinated and instructed the Shiite militias in Syria. Iran's position in Syria gives it easy access to Lebanon and the Mediterranean, so facilitating the achievement of its strategic objectives in the area (Gause, 2019).

An analysis of the Houthi Movement in Yemen and its influence on the surrounding region. The Houthi movement in Yemen serves as a significant component of Iran's aim to expand its influence in the region. Iran's assistance for the Houthis, who are affiliated with the Shiite Zaydi sect in Yemen, is intended to exert pressure on Saudi Arabia and the Gulf nations. Iran offers military supplies, training, and financial assistance to the Houthis. This assistance has empowered the Houthis to withstand the Saudi-led coalition in the Yemeni civil conflict. The Houthis serve as Iran's surrogate force in the area and contribute to the destabilization of Saudi Arabia's southern frontier (Guzansky, 2020).

- Influence on the regional distribution of power: The civil conflict in Yemen is seen as a manifestation of the ongoing power struggle between Iran and Saudi Arabia in the region. The Houthis' alliance with Iran is seen as a direct affront to Saudi Arabia's interests in Yemen, exacerbating sectarian tensions in the area. Moreover, Iran's endeavors to acquire influence in an area next to the Red Sea heighten the security apprehensions of the Gulf nations (Ulrichsen, 2020).

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The strategic goals of Iran and the international reactions

The regional expansion plan pursued by Iran significantly disrupts the prevailing balance of power in the Middle East and elicits a response from the international community. Iran is implementing a plan that involves establishing an anti-Western alliance and adopting a stance that poses a danger to the security of Israel.

Iran's ultimate objective is to develop a dominant influence in the Middle East by creating a Shiite axis and achieving regional hegemony. This objective aligns with Iran's aspiration for ideological expansion and seeks to establish steadfast governments and armed factions across the area. Saudi Arabia and other Sunni Arab nations see this scenario as a significant threat and are actively forming strategic partnerships to limit Iran's regional sway (Kamrava, 2020). The response of the United States and Western countries: The United States and Western nations are carefully observing Iran's plan of expanding its influence in the area and are implementing several steps to counteract it. To limit Iran's influence, the United States provides military assistance to its regional allies and enforces economic sanctions on Iran. Furthermore, international accords, such as the 2015 nuclear deal, also seek to regulate Iran's regional growth agenda. Nevertheless, Iran seems resolute in persisting with this tactic, hence exacerbating tensions in the Middle East (Gause, 2019).

The Prospects of Iran's Strategy for Regional Expansion

Iran seeks to augment its sway and extend its Shia dominance via its regional expansion policy in the Middle East. This tactic is evident throughout a broad geographical area that spans from Lebanon to Yemen, using Iran's allies and proxy armies. Nevertheless, the Sunni Arab nations in the area, Israel, and the Western countries see this tactic as a significant threat, which adds extra complexity to the power dynamics in the Middle East. The regional expansion plan of Iran remains a crucial factor in determining the future of the Middle East. The evolution of this strategy plays a vital role in maintaining peace and security in the area.

United States' policy towards the Middle East

For several years, the United States has actively engaged in the Middle East and has formulated its regional strategy based on a range of strategic objectives. The main objectives are to guarantee Israel's security, halt Iran's nuclear development, and counteract terrorism. Nevertheless, in recent years, the United States has implemented measures to decrease its military footprint in the Middle East. This shift in approach has fundamentally altered the distribution of power in the area and opened up possibilities for other international players.

Security in Israel

The primary objective of the United States' Middle East strategy is to guarantee the security of Israel. Israel is often regarded as the United States' most intimate partner in the Middle East, and the relationship between the two nations has evolved via a strategic partnership since the Cold War.

- The United States offers Israel substantial military support and defense cooperation, giving billions of dollars each year to provide modern weaponry and military equipment, therefore bolstering Israel's defensive capabilities. Furthermore, the United States and Israel often engage in collaborative military drills, demonstrating their extensive defense partnership. The Iron Dome, a missile defense system provided by the US to Israel, plays a crucial role in bolstering Israel's security in the area (Guzansky, 2019).
- Diplomatic Assistance: The United States provides robust assistance to Israel in navigating diplomatic problems on the global stage. This support addresses significant matters, including the use of the prerogative to reject proposed resolutions against Israel at the United Nations. Furthermore, the United States often safeguards Israel's interests in its conflicts with Arab nations and Palestine (Gause, 2019).

Argument

Blocking Iran's Nuclear Program

Iran is seen as a major adversary of the United States in the Middle East, and the United States' policies in the area are heavily focused on Iran's nuclear program. The United States is using many measures to hinder Iran's acquisition of nuclear weapons.

The Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA), reached in 2015 between the P5+1 nations and Iran, was a notable diplomatic achievement with the goal of restricting Iran's nuclear program. Nevertheless, the decision made by US President Donald Trump to withdraw from this deal in 2018 resulted in the reinstatement of economic sanctions, so intensifying the pressure on Iran. The objective of the US sanctions is to undermine the Iranian economy and compel the nation to relinquish its nuclear program (Maloney, 2018).

- **Military Deterrence:** The United States also considers the possibility of using military force to prevent Iran from developing nuclear weapons. American military outposts in the Middle East serve as integral components of the deterrence strategy aimed at countering Iran. Furthermore, the US Navy's presence in the Strait of Hormuz serves the purpose of restricting Iran's military operations in the area (Fitzpatrick, 2020).

Combatting Terrorism

After the September 11, 2001 attacks, combating terrorism became a focal point in US strategy towards the Middle East. The United States carried out massive military campaigns against Al-Qaeda, ISIS, and other extremist terrorist groups. Additionally, the US launched invasions in Afghanistan and Iraq as part of these efforts.

Military campaigns conducted to combat ISIS in Iraq and Syria: In 2014, the United States initiated an extensive military campaign in reaction to the rapid proliferation of ISIS in Iraq and Syria. The military operations have successfully regained much of the land formerly held by

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ISIS, while there are still obstacles to fully eradicating the group. The United States has collaborated with Kurdish parties and local militias in these military actions and has established a partnership with the YPG in Syria (Mazzetti, 2020).

China: A Nation of Subtle Influence and Strategic Economic Diplomacy

China is implementing a policy that refrains from engaging in military actions in the Middle East, while simultaneously bolstering its presence in the area via the expansion of its economic and diplomatic clout. China's Middle East strategy is primarily focused on ensuring energy security, exerting control over trade routes, and enhancing economic links via the "One Belt, One Road" (OBOR) plan. China is expanding its influence in this area via the strategic use of economic diplomacy and soft power, rather than relying on military actions. This strategy might be characterized as a kind of "silent power".

The Middle East plays a crucial role in ensuring energy security

The Middle East is of utmost importance in China's effort to ensure its energy security. China, being one of the top energy users globally, relies heavily on imports from the Middle East for a significant share of its oil and natural gas supply.

China has established enduring energy agreements with major oil and natural gas producers in the Middle East to guarantee the security of its energy supply. China relies heavily on Saudi Arabia, Iran, Iraq, and the United Arab Emirates for its energy needs. China considers energy collaboration with these nations to be a strategic imperative in order to guarantee a consistent and uninterrupted supply of energy resources (Brookings, 2021).

China is now making significant investments in energy infrastructure in the Middle East. Chinese energy firms are actively engaged in initiatives such as the advancement of oil and natural gas reserves in the Middle East and the establishment of refineries and petrochemical

plants. These investments enhance China's ability to obtain energy resources in the area and enhance the security of its energy supply (INSS, 2020).

The "One Belt, One Road" initiative aims to establish trade routes and promote economic connectivity.

China's approach in the Middle East is primarily influenced by its "One Belt, One Road" (OBOR) plan, which seeks to enhance land and maritime trade routes connecting Asia, Africa, and Europe, while also expanding China's economic sway in these areas. The Middle East plays a crucial role in China's One Belt One Road (OBOR) program, namely in terms of land and sea trade routes. China views the Middle East as a crucial link connecting Asia, Africa, and Europe, and is actively striving to transform this area into a strategically important trade route as part of the One Belt One Road (OBOR) initiative. China is now making significant expenditures in the construction of ports, trains, and highways in the area (Kamrava, 2020).

China has entered into extensive trade and investment agreements with Middle Eastern nations in order to boost its trade volume. China is strengthening economic collaboration with nations including Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Iran, and Egypt, and is actively engaged in significant infrastructure initiatives inside these countries. China's trade volume with the Middle East reaches billions of dollars each year and is projected to grow much more as part of the OBOR strategy (Wehrey, 2018).

Collaboration and Disputes Among Muslim Nations

The historical dynamics of Muslim nations have been influenced by a combination of collaboration and discord. Countries in the Middle East, North Africa, and Asia that follow the Islamic faith have historically had theological and cultural connections. However, they have also faced significant conflicts arising from divergent political agendas, sectarian divides, and attempts for regional dominance. Nevertheless, ongoing efforts to collaborate among these nations persist via many regional and international forums.

Common Religious and Cultural Ties

- The foundation of collaboration among Muslim nations lies in the shared faith of Islam and a collective cultural legacy. This shared foundation serves as a robust framework for unity and collaboration across nations.
- The Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) is an international organization that brings together countries with a majority Muslim population. The Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) was established in 1969 with the objective of fostering collaboration among countries in the Islamic world. It serves as a crucial forum for Muslim nations. The organization's objective is to enhance economic, political, and cultural collaboration among member nations. Nevertheless, the efficacy of the organization might be constrained by political disputes and divergences among member nations (Esposito, 2019).
- Economic and commerce Cooperation: Economic collaboration among Muslim nations mostly focuses on energy commerce, agriculture, and industry. The Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) fosters economic integration and collaboration among its member nations. Nevertheless, political disagreements might sometimes impede economic collaboration (Kamrava, 2020).

Religious divisions and conflicts between different regions

The Sunni-Shia sectarian split is a significant distinction among Muslim nations that serves as the underlying cause of several crises and political problems in the area.

• Saudi Arabia and Iran, as the dominant nations representing Sunni and Shia Islam respectively, are now involved in a regional power war. The antagonism between these two nations has resulted in proxy conflicts in nations such as Yemen, Syria, Iraq, and Lebanon. Saudi Arabia asserts its dominance in the Sunni Arab world, while Iran seeks to extend its influence among Shia communities. This competition is a prominent factor contributing to the instability in the Middle East (Wehrey, 2018).

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- Gulf Countries experiencing heightened tensions: Periodically, there are significant conflicts among Gulf nations. In 2017, Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Bahrain, and Egypt enforced a diplomatic and economic blockade on Qatar, resulting in a deterioration in collaboration among the Gulf nations. Qatar defied the ban by forging strong alliances with Iran and Turkey. This friction resulted in a profound schism among the nations in the Gulf area (Ulrichsen, 2020).

International Cooperation and Conflict Areas

- The collaboration among Muslim nations has a significant impact both at the regional and global levels. Nevertheless, this collaboration sometimes gets entangled in several international disputes and rivalries.
- The Palestinian conflict and its relationship with Muslim nations: The Palestinian problem has always been seen as a shared concern among Muslim nations, and there has been extensive unity and support over this matter. Nevertheless, the process of normalization between some Arab nations and Israel has undermined the solidarity among Muslim countries with the Palestinian struggle, resulting in the creation of diverse perspectives on this matter (Sayigh, 2021).
- Counter-terrorism and Security Cooperation: Muslim nations collaborate in combating global terrorism. Nevertheless, this collaboration may sometimes be undermined as a result of political agendas and ideological disparities. Counterterrorism operations have been conducted against extremist groups, including ISIS and Al-Qaeda, while there is still inadequate security collaboration among some nations (Gerges, 2019).

Gulf Countries and Regional Competition

The competition among Saudi Arabia, Qatar, and the United Arab Emirates (UAE) in the Gulf area has had a significant impact on the political equilibrium in the Middle East. The power

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competition among these nations has significantly disrupted collaboration and alliances in the area, posing a danger to regional security.

Rivalry Between Saudi Arabia, UAE and Qatar

- Saudi Arabia and the UAE are leading the Gulf nations in regional leadership, but Qatar is competing with them by pursuing an autonomous foreign policy. Qatar has strengthened its ties with Turkey and Iran in response to the diplomatic and economic blockade imposed by Saudi Arabia, the UAE, Bahrain, and Egypt in 2017. Turkey has provided military assistance to Qatar, but Iran has supplied economic and logistical aid to Qatar. Qatar's attempts to isolate itself have been hindered, leading to increased rivalry in the area (Ulrichsen, 2020).
- Diplomatic Crises and the Erosion of the GCC: The ongoing conflict between Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and the UAE has significantly undermined the efficacy of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC). Despite its establishment in 1981 with the aim of enhancing economic, military, and political collaboration among the Gulf nations, the Qatar issue has significantly undermined the cohesion and decision-making processes of the GCC. The diminished strength of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) has hindered collaborative efforts in the area and endangered the security of the region (Kamrava, 2020).

Regional and Global Reflections

- The ongoing conflict between Saudi Arabia, Qatar, and the UAE has had significant repercussions both inside the region and on a worldwide scale, ultimately impacting the geopolitical dynamics of the Middle East.
- Regional Power Dynamics: Saudi Arabia and the UAE attempted to alter the regional power dynamics in their favor by imposing an embargo on Qatar. However, Qatar's

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alliances with Turkey and Iran have thwarted these efforts, rendering them ineffectual. This has resulted in increased polarization and conflicts for power in the Gulf area (Wehrey, 2018).

- **Global Impacts:** The rivalry among the Gulf nations has had repercussions on worldwide energy markets and international diplomacy. Given that the Gulf area has the most substantial deposits of oil and natural gas globally, any conflicts among these nations may have a direct impact on energy prices and the overall stability of the global economy. Furthermore, this struggle has significant significance in the Middle East strategy of key global powers such as the United States, Russia, China, and the European Union (Gause, 2019).

Dynamics Between Türkiye, Iran and Saudi Arabia

The interactions among Turkey, Iran, and Saudi Arabia in the Middle East are crucial in determining the distribution of power in the area. Although these three nations vie for regional dominance, they sometimes sporadically collaborate on shared goals. These dynamics have a direct impact on the political, military, and economic equilibrium in the Middle East.

The Origins of Regional Competition

- Turkey, Iran, and Saudi Arabia are engaged in intense rivalry as they vie for power and control in the Middle East, despite their divergent historical, religious, and political backgrounds.
- **Sectarian and Political Differences:** Saudi Arabia asserts its leadership in Sunni Islam, while Iran serves as the primary representation of Shia Islam. The sectarian divide is evident in proxy conflicts occurring in countries like Syria, Yemen, and Iraq, and it intensifies the rivalry between the two nations (Wehrey, 2018). Contrarily, Turkey has

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a strategy aimed at achieving equilibrium between secularism and Islamism, and maintains its contacts with these two nations across several domains (Altunışık, 2019).

- The competition for regional dominance: Turkey, Iran, and Saudi Arabia are using distinct methods in their quest to establish themselves as leaders in the Middle East. Saudi Arabia asserts its leadership via the use of its economic might and influence within the Islamic world, while Iran seeks to disseminate its revolution and extend its military might across the region. Contrarily, Turkey persistently strives for regional dominance by using its historical legacy and strategic geographical position (Kamrava, 2020).

The Future of Regional Alliances

The current alliances in the Middle East might be reconfigured to align with shifting regional and global forces. The creation of alliances is primarily influenced by national interests, ideological disagreements, and security concerns of nations in the area. Within this particular framework, the Turkey-Qatar and Saudi Arabia-UAE alliances will persistently impact the equilibrium in the area. Simultaneously, Iran's efforts to enhance its regional influence may result in the establishment of new counter-alliances. This might potentially heighten the likelihood of war in the area.

The alliance between Turkey and Qatar

The connection between Turkey and Qatar has emerged as one of the most robust and enduring alliances in the region in recent years. The partnership has significantly strengthened, particularly since the imposition of an embargo on Qatar by Saudi Arabia and the UAE.

- Strategic and Military Cooperation: Turkey's provision of military assistance to Qatar serves as a significant security assurance, including both military and diplomatic aspects. The presence of the Turkish military installation in Qatar serves as a tangible manifestation of the alliance between the two nations and strengthens their strategic collaboration (Ulrichsen, 2020).

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- Economic Cooperation: Turkey and Qatar engage in extensive collaboration in sectors like energy, banking, and commerce. Qatar makes substantial investments in the Turkish economy, and in return, Turkey actively contributes to Qatar's infrastructure initiatives. This economic collaboration enhances the connections between the two nations (Kamrava, 2020).

Saudi Arabia-UAE Alliance

The Gulf area has been significantly impacted by the formidable partnership between Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates (UAE), resulting in a substantial effect on regional affairs. These two nations are especially determined to offset Iran's regional influence.

Security and Defense Cooperation: Saudi Arabia and the UAE collaborate extensively in military and security matters to restrict Iran's regional influence. The combined actions of these two nations in the Yemeni civil war exemplify the military aspect of this partnership (Wehrey, 2018).

Saudi Arabia and the UAE engage in economic and political cooperation via their membership in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC). The two nations seek to establish stability and security in the Gulf area via the coordination of economic and political policies. Nevertheless, it has been noted that this coalition sometimes gives rise to conflicts with neighboring nations in the area (Ulrichsen, 2020).

Iran's Quest for Influence and New Counter-Alliances

Iran has consistently maintained an assertive foreign policy with the aim of extending its influence in the Middle East, resulting in the emergence of new counter-alliances in the area. Iran is strategically seeking to expand its influence in Iraq, Syria, Lebanon, and Yemen by using Shia parties in these regions. This effort is sometimes referred to as the Shia Crescent. This

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approach is a component of Iran's efforts to establish a sphere of influence known as the "Shia Crescent" (Wehrey, 2018).

Iran's expansionist endeavors have prompted nations like Saudi Arabia, the UAE, Israel, and even Turkey to establish counter-alliances. These counter-alliances have the objective of counteracting Iran's influence in the region and are continuously altering the distribution of power in the area (Kamrava, 2020).

The Future of Regional Conflicts

The persistent internal conflicts in nations such as Syria, Yemen, and Libya within the Middle East persist as the primary catalyst for instability in the area. Regional players and global powers have varying impacts and influences on these wars. The future trajectory of these conflicts will be determined by the choices made by the nations in the area as well as the global powers. The future hinges on the success of peace efforts and the consequential influence of these wars on the area.

Syrian Civil War

The ongoing Syrian civil war is one of the most intricate and devastating wars in the Middle East. The conflict has evolved into a proxy war, with several regional and global entities involved, resulting in severe humanitarian problems inside the nation.

Current Situation and Positions of the Parties: The ongoing conflict in Syria is a complex and multifaceted conflict involving several actors, including the Assad government, opposition factions, terrorist organizations such as ISIS, and Kurdish troops. The Assad administration, bolstered by the backing of Russia and Iran, has successfully recaptured authority over the majority of the nation. Nevertheless, the battle in Syria remains focused on the northern areas

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mostly because of the involvement of Kurdish troops supported by the United States and Turkey (Wehrey, 2018).

Efforts to secure a durable peace in Syria have been undertaken via diplomatic initiatives such as the Astana Process and the Geneva Talks. Nevertheless, the level of success that these procedures will achieve is unpredictable because of the profound distrust amongst the parties involved and the interventions from other sources. If long-term peace cannot be attained in Syria, it has the potential to adversely impact other conflicts in the area (Kamrava, 2020).

Yemen Civil War

Yemen, a nation in the Middle East, is now grappling with a significant humanitarian crisis. The military actions carried out by the Saudi-led coalition against the Houthis have resulted in a severe humanitarian catastrophe.

The crisis in Yemen is a manifestation of the sectarian and regional rivalry between Saudi Arabia and Iran. Saudi Arabia engaged in military involvement against the Houthis in Yemen with the aim of thwarting Iran's efforts to expand its influence in the area. However, this engagement only worsened the conflict (Gause, 2019).

Future Peace Possibilities: The attainment of peace in Yemen relies on the positive involvement of the international community and regional players in this endeavor. Nevertheless, given the present circumstances, attaining an enduring state of tranquility in Yemen seems to be challenging. The current scenario is likely to have enduring adverse consequences for the bordering nations of Yemen and the overall stability in the Middle East (Wehrey, 2018).

Civil War in Libya

The civil war that ensued in Libya after the ousting of the Gaddafi dictatorship in 2011 has resulted in the nation being split into two primary factions: One faction is the Government of National Accord (GNA) located in Tripoli, while the other faction is the Libyan National Army (LNA) led by General Khalifa Haftar.

Regional and International Interventions: The crisis in Libya has evolved into a proxy war, with Turkey and Qatar providing assistance to the GNA, while Egypt, the UAE, and Russia are backing Haftar. These developments have exacerbated the complexity of the civil conflict in Libya and hindered the peace process (Kamrava, 2020).

The peace process and future scenarios: Despite the United Nations-led peace negotiations providing optimism for a lasting resolution in Libya, significant divisions between the involved parties and outsider actions pose challenges to this process. The attainment of enduring peace in Libya relies not alone on the constructive involvement of local factions but also on the participation of foreign players (Wehrey, 2018).

Regional and Global Reflections

The outcome of these wars in the Middle East has significant implications for both regional stability and global security. The long-term trajectory of the civil conflicts in Syria, Yemen, and Libya hinges on the choices made by regional nations and the involvement of the international community in the settlement processes.

The wars in the Middle East are continuously altering the regional balance of power. Specifically, the rivalry among Iran, Saudi Arabia, Turkey, and other regional players amplifies the impact of these nations on the ongoing crises. There is a possibility that this might result in ongoing unrest in the area (Kamrava, 2020).

Global Impacts

The wars in the Middle East have a direct impact on worldwide oil markets, refugee problems, and international terrorism. Hence, the outcome of the crises in Syria, Yemen, and Libya has immense significance, not only for the Middle East, but also for global security and stability (Gause, 2019).

Strategic Insights and Recommendations

The Middle East is a very significant area in global politics because to its abundant oil resources, key geopolitical position, and long-standing historical conflicts. The dynamics in the area are influenced by the strategic actions of both local and international players and will heavily impact the future configuration of the Middle East. Hence, it is crucial to carefully observe the progress in the area, do thorough strategic assessments, and assess these studies within a global framework in order to comprehend the future dynamics of the Middle East. To attain peace and stability, it is imperative to intensify diplomatic efforts and enhance the efficacy of dialogue structures. The international community should take on a greater role in order to discover viable solutions to the humanitarian problems in the Middle East and bring an end to wars. Furthermore, it is essential for the construction of enduring tranquility and steadiness that nations in the area enhance their collaboration with one another, devise shared resolutions to regional issues, and provide the groundwork for these resolutions to be durable. This research has conducted a thorough analysis of the strategic equilibriums in the Middle East, the strategic methodologies used by the players in the area, and the worldwide ramifications of these methodologies. This study offers a comprehensive framework, backed by academic research and substantial literature studies, to enhance our understanding of the dynamics in the Middle East area and assess potential future scenarios. To enhance the analysis and get a more profound comprehension of the area, future study should concentrate on particular nations or conflict sites in the Middle East. Specifically, a thorough analysis of particular matters such as energy policy, water resource disputes, and religious and

ethnic conflicts would provide a clearer understanding of how the Middle East influences global security and economic stability.

To summarize, the strategic analyses offered in this paper serve as a strong basis for further research in the area of political science and offer the essential academic framework to comprehend the power dynamics in the Middle East. By doing more research and delving into a certain location or issue, a more thorough understanding of the strategic power struggle in the Middle East may be achieved. Research in this field will provide more accurate forecasts on the future trajectory of the area and its position in global affairs, hence aiding the formulation of better informed plans by regional and global policymakers.

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